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Purpose of this document: Provide instructions to quality control the dating table of the SISAL database after issues were identified

(see companion Excel file and

https://github.com/jensfohlmeister/QC_SISALv2_dating_metadata for further details)

Date of last edits: July 2019

References:

- Atsawawaranunt, K., Comas-Bru, L., Amirnezhad Mozhdehi, S., Deininger, M., Harrison, S. P., Baker, A., Boyd, M., Kaushal, N., Ahmad, S. M., Ait Brahim, Y., Arienzo, M., Bajo, P., Braun, K., Burstyn, Y., Chawchai, S., Duan, W., Hatvani, I. G., Hu, J., Kern, Z., Labuhn, I., Lachniet, M., Lechleitner, F. A., Lorrey, A., Pérez-Mejías, C., Pickering, R., Scroxton, N., and SISAL Working Group Members: The SISAL database: a global resource to document oxygen and carbon isotope records from speleothems, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 10, 1687–1713, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-10-1687-2018>, 2018.
- Comas-Bru, L., Harrison, S. P., Werner, M., Rehfeld, K., Scroxton, N., Veiga-Pires, C., and SISAL working group members: Evaluating model outputs using integrated global speleothem records of climate change since the last glacial, *Clim. Past*, 15, 1557–1579, <https://doi.org/10.5194/cp-15-1557-2019>, 2019.

Dataset:

- Comas-Bru, L., Atsawawaranunt, K., Harrison, S. and SISAL working group members (2020): SISAL (Speleothem Isotopes Synthesis and Analysis Working Group) database version 2.0. University of Reading. Dataset. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17864/1947.242>

DOI: <https://10.5281/zenodo.3631443>

ACTION 1: Atomic activities vs activity ratio

PROBLEM: SISAL dating info should always report activity ratios (as described in the first row of the workbook, see <https://10.5281/zenodo.3631403>), but several entities in the database are currently reporting atomic ratios.

Most laboratories report $[^{230}\text{Th}]/[^{232}\text{Th}]$ as an activity ratio e.g. with the square brackets. However, at least one lab (University of Queensland) report $^{230}\text{Th}/^{232}\text{Th}$ as an atomic ratio (e.g. without the square brackets).

In all papers, where Hai Cheng and Larry Edwards are involved, they provide the atomic ratio of $^{230}\text{Th}/^{232}\text{Th}$ and in the header of the column they say all numbers are $10e-6$. Unfortunately, this power is not always accounted for in the conversion to activity ratio done for SISAL.

TASK:

Quickly check the source publications to confirm that $[^{230}\text{Th}/^{232}\text{Th}]$ (e.g. activity ratio) is reported (sometimes this is hard to tell).

Please, do so as well for the assumed initial $[^{230}\text{Th}/^{232}\text{Th}]$. This is often missing as well or inserted as atomic ratios.

If atomic ratios are definitely reported, and these have been incorrectly added to the SISAL workbook as activity ratios $[^{230}\text{Th}]/[^{232}\text{Th}]$ and/or the $10\text{e-}6$ power has not taken into account, please revise and resubmit.

It is important to make sure that we use the decay constant mentioned in the papers to convert from atomic ratio to activity ratio (see the tabs in the calculator file attached). Note that the former version of the calculator was only able to transform one notation into the next with the latest decay constants (i.e., Cheng et al., 2013). We have now updated this to include the most common decay variables (Cheng et al., 2000 and Cheng et al., 2013). Please use the relevant tab according to the decay constant in the paper.

Tip: Any number with a 10 to minus 5 or minus 6 attached is an atomic ratio because these are always small numbers when the numerator is the radiogenic isotope (e.g. ^{230}Th , ^{234}U).

Something to watch out for: The convention should be that round brackets are used for activity ratios (not square). However, this is not always the case.

ACTION 2: Is $[^{234}\text{U}]/[^{238}\text{U}]$ missing in a SISAL entity?

PROBLEM: For quite a lot of speleothem dating points the $^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ activity ratio is not provided. This is necessary to re-calculate individual ages (e.g., due to the use of a not-actual value of the decay constants of earlier publications). In some cases, the fact that the $^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ activity ratio is missing in the SISAL database is especially strange, as the delta notation (i.e., $\delta^{234}\text{U}$) values are reported in the paper. In addition, in some cases, $\delta^{234}\text{U}$ was provided in the dating sheets instead of $^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ activity ratio, further highlighting the need of double checking this column if we want to have a usable long-lasting database!

TASK:

Go through publications of the entities and check whether delta-243U is reported. Convert these to $^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ activities for as many records as you can.

It is easy to convert from one to the other. For delta ^{234}U ($\delta^{234}\text{U}$), you just need to divide the value by 1000, and then add 1, and you will have $[^{234}\text{U}]/[^{238}\text{U}]$. See relevant tab in Excel sheet attached for easy calculation.

Something to watch out for: Some papers report initial $\delta^{234}\text{U}$ ($\delta^{234}\text{U}_i$) instead of measured $\delta^{234}\text{U}$ (which is what you need to calculate the age). Do not use $\delta^{234}\text{U}_i$ for the conversion
